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Title: Combined *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity and severity of the objective circumstances related to the suicide attempt

Running Title: *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* and suicide severity

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Abstract

This study examines for the first time whether a high *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity combination increases the likelihood of suicidal intent severity. Survivors of a suicide attempt (n=587; 86.8% women) were genotyped for *CYP2C19* (*2, *17) and *CYP2D6* (*3, *4, *4xN, *5, *6, *10, *wtxN) and evaluated with the Beck Suicide Intent Scale (SIS). Patients with a high *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity showed an increased risk for a severe attempt ($p < 0.01$) as measured by the SIS-objective circumstances subscale (OR=1.37; 1.05-1.78; $p = 0.02$) after adjusting for confounders (gender, age, level of studies, marital status, mental disorders, tobacco use, family history of suicide, personal history of attempts and violence of the attempt). Furthermore, the risk was greater in those without a family history of suicide (OR=1.82; 95% CI=1.19-2.77; $p = 0.002$). Further research remains to determine whether the observed relationship is mediated by the role of *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* in the endogenous and/or drug metabolism.

Keywords: pharmacogenomics, cytochrome P450, *CYP2C19*, *CYP2D6*, severity of suicide, Beck-Suicide intention scale.

Introduction

Suicide completion,¹ lifetime history of suicide attempts,² suicidal risk,³ and the severity of the objective circumstances related to the suicide attempt⁴ have been found to be more likely in subjects with an increased number of *CYP2D6* active genes, who are assumed to have a high enzyme activity in drug metabolism/elimination.

CYP2D6 is not only involved in the exogenous metabolism of many Central Nervous System (CNS) medications such as most antidepressants, antipsychotics, opioids, etc. (Llerena et al., 2009),⁵ but also of endogenous neuroactive substances.^{6,7} Thus, the effect of *CYP2D6* on suicidal behaviour can be partially due to drug therapeutic failure during treatment with *CYP2D6* substrates, to differences in the CNS regulation, or to both of them. In support of these later hypotheses, variability in *CYP2D6* has been linked to differences in personality traits, neurocognitive functions and mental disorders.⁶ Furthermore, several studies have found poor response to antidepressant drugs or early dropout from monotherapy treatment with *CYP2D6* antidepressant substrates in ultrarapid metabolizers.⁸⁻¹² Despite above evidence, negative findings have been also reported for the association of *CYP2D6* genotypes with either response to drug treatment,^{13,14} or history of suicidal behaviors.^{15,16} However, these later studies presented significant differences in the population, genotyping procedures and/or the definition of main variables, which have been already substantially discussed elsewhere.¹⁷ Besides, an additional limitation common to all studies genotyping for *CYP2D6* is that gene duplication only identifies about 30-40% ultrarapid metabolizers for *CYP2D6*.^{18,19} Besides *CYP2D6*, other polymorphic enzymes that are also known to be simultaneously involved in the metabolism of endogenous and exogenous psychoactive substances could be taken into account for the pharmacogenomics of

suicide. In keeping with that, the combined effect of CYP2D6 with CYP2C19 should be studied since the latter is also involved in the metabolism of psychoactive drugs used for the relief of anxious and depressive symptoms such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, tricyclic antidepressants, and other like benzodiazepines.²⁰ Furthermore, CYP2C19 plays also a role in metabolizing CNS substrates. CYP2C19's expression has been recently shown in the human fetal brain.²¹ Additionally, CYP2C19 has been shown to participate in the metabolism of endogenous steroids and cannabinoid-like compounds,²⁰ which might underlie the observed alterations in brain development and affective behavior observed in a transgenic mouse model carrying the human *CYP2C19*.²¹ Consistently, individuals who do not produce CYP2C19 because they are homozygous for the null protein activity allele *2 self-reported lower levels of depressive symptoms.²² In order to evaluate the combined influence of these two highly polymorphic genes involved in the metabolism of CNS drugs and substances, a helpful strategy might be based on calculating a “drug metabolic capacity score”, which we will propose.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate for the first time whether there is a relationship between the presently proposed combined metabolic capacity of *CYP2C19* and *CYP2D6* (classified into “high”, “medium” and “low”) and the severity of the suicide attempt.

Patients and methods

A total of 587 suicide attempters (86.9% women; mean age 37.5 ± 12.2 years old) with 12.5 (± 4.6) years of education corresponding to secondary school completion were evaluated in a specialized unit of the Montpellier University Hospital. Other sociodemographic data such as marital status and the most frequent DSM-IV Axis I

mental disorders as assessed by the Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) and current tobacco smoking use are described in Table 3, All individuals but 3 met diagnostic criteria of at least one mental disorder, with a 41.3% meeting criteria for two and 44.1% for more than two. All were French speaking and had four biological grandparents originating from Western European countries. All participants gave written informed consent, as approved by the local Ethic Committees, after receiving information on the study.

Evaluation of Suicide

Patients were evaluated with the Beck Suicide Intent Scale (SIS)²³ within the initial hours of a failed suicide attempt. This questionnaire consists of 15 items rated on a three-point scale (0, 1 or 2), which are divided into two subscales. The first section, "objective circumstances", assesses the severity of the characteristics related to the suicidal act or the active preparation or planning of the attempt such as isolation, timing, suicide notes and precautions against discovery and intervention. It is of note that a high score in this subscale has shown predictive validity for eventual suicide.²³ The second section, "conception", assesses the individual's awareness and emotional memories of the suicidal act (purpose, expectations of fatality, attitude about death, etc.). A suicide attempt was defined as "a self-destructive behavior with intent to end one's life independent of resulting damage".

Suicide attempts were classified as violent if involving firearms, drowning, cutting, jumping or hanging. Patients were also asked about the family history of suicide attempts including suicide completion and suicide attempts in first, second and third-degree relatives, personal history of suicidal behaviors and the age of the first suicide attempt.

CYP2D6 and *CYP2C19* genotyping

Patients were genotyped for polymorphisms in the *CYP2C19* related to null (mainly *2) and increased protein activity in drug metabolism (*17) and in the *CYP2D6* related to null (*3, *4, *4xN, *5, *6) decreased (*10) or increased (*wtxN) protein activity in the Clinical Research Center of Extremadura University Hospital Medical School (as described below). The *CYP2D6* genotypes were analyzed in accordance with previously described methods.²⁴ The *CYP2D6* genotyping analysis was performed by amplifying the entire *CYP2D6* gene using extra-long PCR for *CYP2D6**5 and multiplication alleles. Subjects positive for a *duplication* were further characterized for gene copy number, using Real-time PCR (as described below). To discriminate between the *CYP2D6*wtxN, and *4xN alleles, we generated a 10-kb long XL-PCR fragment from duplication-positive subjects and tested these for the respective SNPs by an established PCR– restriction fragment length polymorphism approach.²⁴ The analysis for the *CYP2D6* *3, *4,*6 and *10 and *CYP2C19* *2 and *17 allelic variants was carried out on genomic DNA using the commercially available TaqMan assays (C_32407232_50, C_27102431_D0, C_32407243_20, and C_11484460_40, C_25986767_70 and C_469857_10). The *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* genotypes were determined based on the presence of “key” single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with the alleles of interest (2549delA, rs35742686; 1846G>A, rs3892097; 1707delT, rs5030655; 100C>T, rs1065852; c681G>A, rs4244285; -806C>T, rs12248560)^{24,25} .

Real time-PCR genotyping was carried out by using Taqman according to the manufacturer’s instructions, including specific primers and probes for these polymorphisms, and the Universal PCR Master Mix, No AmpErase UNG, which contains AmpliTaq Gold DNA polymerase, dNTP, buffers, and passive internal

reference based on the ROX reference dye (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). The amplification conditions to detect *CYP2D6* *3, *4, *6 and *10 and *CYP2C19**2 alleles consisted of a 10-min pre-incubation at 95°C to activate the Taq DNA polymerase, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 92°C for 15 s and then by primer annealing and extension for 1 min at 60°C. To identify the *CYP2C19**17 allele, the same conditions of pre-incubation were used, but the conditions of denaturation and of annealing and extension were 45 cycles at 92°C for 15 s and at 60°C for 1 min, respectively. To characterize the *CYP2D6* gene copy number, the same reagents were used, except the use of *CYP2D6* Copy Number assays (Hs00010001_cn; Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA) and passive internal reference based on the ROX reference dye (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). The same conditions of pre-incubation and extension were used, but the conditions of denaturation were 40 cycles at 95°C for 15 s. Hs00010001_cn specifically targets *CYP2D6* exon 9 sequences and will not amplify *CYP2D7* or *CYP2D8* pseudogenes, or *CYP2D6* alleles having *CYP2D7* sequences in exon 9 (e.g., *CYP2D6**36). All assays were carried out in 96 well plates, with each plate including no template control (NTC, without DNA) and positive (heterozygous and/or homozygous) controls. Plates were read on an ABI 7300 instrument (Applied Biosystems).

Subjects' classification into *high, medium, low CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity

Table 1 shows the assigned “activity” values for *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* alleles . The combined drug metabolic capacity score was calculated for each individual based on the assigned values for *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19*. The *CYP2D6* activity score system is based on the values previously proposed by Gaedigk et al. (2008),²⁶ and later confirmed in Hispanics.¹⁸ Regarding the drug metabolic capacity score for exploring the overall effect of *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* on suicide severity, we propose a new system (Table

1, Figure 1) on the basis of two other previously suggested evaluating their effect on different outcomes.^{27,28} It is highlighted that the previous studies did not determine the presence of *CYP2D6 duplications*²⁷ or *CYP2C19*17*,²⁸ which are of relevance for the present work. Finally, once calculated the sum of the *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* allele activity scores, individuals were classified into three groups characterized by having a: “high” metabolic capacity corresponding to a drug metabolic capacity score above 4, “medium” corresponding to a score equal to 4 or “low” corresponding to a score lower than 4. Figure 1 shows the definition of the combined *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* genotypes based on the three categories.

Insert Table 1 about here

Insert Figure 1 about here

Data analysis

The scores of the SIS subscales (outcome) were firstly explored as a continuous measure and later categorized into binary variables as in our previous studies in Spain. Suicide attempters were classified as those scoring at the 75th percentile in both scales the SIS- "objective circumstances" and the "conception" sections.^{4,29} In the present study the 75th percentile for the "objective circumstances" section corresponded to a score equal to 8, whereas in the previous study was of 7, and for the "conception" section was of 12, whereas in the previous study was of 11.⁴ Finally, a binary logistic regression model was used to test the contribution of the combined metabolic capacity

score on the severity of the suicide intent adjusting for all the variables measured (gender, age, marital status, level of studies, mental disorders, tobacco use, family history of suicide, personal history of suicide attempts and violence of the attempt).

Results

Evaluation of Suicide

Individuals' mean scores on the SIS-"objective circumstances" section was 6.2 ± 3.2 , on the "conception" was 9.5 ± 3.7 and the "global" was 15.5 ± 6.1 . Of the total sample, 15.7% showed violent suicide intent, and 48% had a family history of suicidal behaviors.

Furthermore, only for 36.4%, this suicide attempt was the first one. The overall mean age of the first attempt was of 29.3 ± 12.9 , and the mean lifetime history of suicide attempts was of 2.9 ± 3.6 in general but 3.9 ± 4.2 for those with 2 or more suicide attempts.

There were no relationships between any of the most frequent DSM-IV Axis I mental disorders reported in Table 3 or the number of them and the dimensional or binary scores of the SIS-"objective circumstances" section.

Evaluation of *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19*

The population was in Hardy Weinberg Equilibrium for *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* alleles (Table 2).

Insert Table 2 about here

The frequencies of individuals with regard to their number of active alleles are shown in Table 5 for *CYP2D6* and in Table 6 for *CYP2C19*.

Evaluation of the relationship between combined CYP2D6-CYP2C19 metabolic capacity and suicide

Initial logistic regression analyses were performed to assess the independent variable of interest (the “low” 37.8%, “medium” 39.2%, “high” 23%, CYP2D6-CYP2C19 metabolic capacity combination) as a predictor for suicide intent ("objective circumstances and "conception") as a continuous measure. The combined metabolic capacity score predicted differences only in the dimension of the "objective circumstances" section of the suicide attempt ($p=0.02$, as shown in Figure 2). However, after adjusting for all variables, no differences were found. Therefore, only the relation of the CYP2D6-CYP2C19 metabolic capacity with the SIS-"objective circumstances" related to the suicide attempt as a binary dependent variable is reported.

Insert Figure 2 about here

The categorical classification of the "objective circumstances" section of the suicide attempt into severe (at percentile 75th and above) and non severe yielded a higher frequency of patients with a “high drug metabolic capacity score” (>4), as well as a lower frequency of those with a “low” metabolism (<4) among those classified as severe suicide attempters ($p<0.01$) as shown in Table 4.

Furthermore, those with a high metabolic capacity showed a higher risk of a severe suicide intent (OR=1.37; 1.05-1.78; $p=0.02$) after controlling for gender, age, level of studies, marital status, mental disorders, tobacco use, family history of suicide, personal history of attempts, age of the first attempt and violence of the attempt. Of these

variables, only family history of suicide significantly contributed to the regression model (OR=1.99; 95% CI=1.35-2.96; p=0.01). Thus, the population was divided into those with and without a family history of suicide, and the risk was further increased in those without such a history (OR=1.82; 95% CI=1.19-2.77; p<0.01). Furthermore, exploratory analyses comparing these two groups showed that those without a family history of suicide had a later mean age for the first attempt (29.8±13.2 vs. 27.4±11.9; p<0.05). In addition, they were less frequent than those with a family history of suicide among those who abused alcohol (p<0.05), or tobacco (p<0.05), or used a violent suicidal method or a severe suicide attempt as assessed by both SIS scales "objective circumstances" (p<0.01) and "conception" (p<0.01).

We also explored whether there was an independent effect of the *CYP2D6* or *CYP2C19* activity scores based categories. There were no significant differences in the distribution of the severe vs. non-severe suicide attempters for *CYP2D6* (Table 5). However, despite there was a higher number of heterozygous individuals carrying the increased activity allele *17 for *CYP2C19* among the severe suicide attempters (p=0.04), this association was not significant when controlling for all confounders (Table 6). Thus, in the present population, suicide severity was not independently associated with the number of *CYP2D6* or *CYP2C19* active allele variants.

Insert Tables 3-6 about here

Discussion

The present study examined whether there were differences in the frequency of individuals with a high, medium or low *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* combined metabolic

capacity score between severe and non-severe suicide attempters. These results show for the first time that there was an association between the *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* combined metabolic groups and the severity of the suicidal intent related to the objective circumstances section. A high *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity was related to increased severity of the suicidal behavior.

Present findings are consistent with the fact that most drugs used for preventing or treating individuals with a history of suicide are metabolized by *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19*, which also participate in the metabolism of CNS endogenous substrates.^{5,6,7,20, 21} However, an important limiting factor of the present study is the lack of data about the individuals' drug treatment and their drug plasma levels. Because most available information about these polymorphic genes is related to drug therapeutic failure, the independent relationship between *CYP2D6* or *CYP2C19* with suicide severity could be expected in those individuals taking drug metabolized by these enzymes.

The present study did not find an independent relation between *CYP2D6* and suicide severity among suicide attempters from France as previously observed in Spain.⁴ This may be related to the fact that the number of individuals with more than two active genes (ultrarapid metabolizers, UMs) was slightly lower than the number of UMs from Spain.⁴ Although, the frequency of UMs in the present population was similar to other reported in Caucasian populations of psychiatric patients studying the relationship between *CYP2D6* and response to antidepressant treatment.^{9,27,30} Then, a likely reason for the lack of association between *CYP2D6* and suicide severity **could** be related to the fact that *CYP2D6 duplication* is reported to be higher in Spain.¹⁸

Regarding the number of *CYP2C19* active alleles, the frequencies of those with an activity score of zero or of more than two in the present population were also very

similar to the frequencies found in other Caucasian populations of psychiatric patients primarily taking antidepressant drugs.^{27,31-35}

Finally, the present result of a relationship between the combined *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity with the severity of the objective circumstances related to suicide most likely occurs in those individuals without a family history of suicidal behavior, who seem to represent a differentiated clinical phenotype of suicide attempters.³⁶ In support of that, it is well known that having a family history of suicidal behavior imposes an additive genetic and environmental risk for suicide, which has been related with a vulnerable personality profile characterized by impulsivity and hopelessness, as well as with early age-related attempts.³⁶ Consistently, those with a family history of suicide in the present study showed an earlier age for the first attempt. In addition, they were more likely to abuse alcohol, smoke tobacco, and to have performed a violent suicide attempt or a severe suicide attempt as measured by SIS. Thus, in the frame of the diathesis-stress model,³⁷ those with no family history of suicide have less vulnerability to suicide and consequently may need more stress triggers to precipitate it. A lower response to medication due to a high CYPs metabolic capacity may increase the burden of mental disorders and stress. However, the study of the relationship between the combined *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity with the severity of the objective circumstances related to the suicide intent needs to be clarified.

In conclusion, a high *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* metabolic capacity increases the severity of the suicide intent, which appears to be especially relevant among those without a family history of suicide. **This result suggests that the combination of *CYP2D6-CYP2C19* could act as a novel mechanism precipitating the likelihood of suicide in those without such genetic predisposition.** These findings support the implementation of the presently proposed metabolic capacity evaluation strategy as a tool for identifying those at

greatest risk for death from suicide. However, further research remains to determine whether the observed relationship is mediated by the role of CYP2D6 and CYP2C19 in the endogenous and/or drug metabolism.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors have no conflict of interest to declare with the exception of Dr. Blasco-Fontecilla, who has received lecture fees from Eli Lilly, AB-Biotics, and Shire.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1. CYP2D6 and CYP2C19 allele activity scores

CYP2D6 alleles	CYP2C19 alleles	Activity Score	Activity Category
*3, *4, *4xN, *5, *6,	*2	0	<i>Null</i>
*10		0.5	<i>Decreased</i>
wt (*1)	wt (*1)	1	<i>Normal</i>
wt(*1)x2	*17	2	<i>Rapid</i>

Table 2. Frequency of CYP2D6 and CYP2C19 allelic variants in a population of 587 individuals who have attempted suicide.

CYP2D6 alleles	Frequency
wt	0,72572
*3	0,00596
*4	0,18910
*5	0,01959
*6	0,00596
*10	0,02044
wtx2	0,03237
*4x2	0,00085
CYP2C19 alleles	Frequency
wt	0,6661
*2	0,1252
*17	0,2087

Table 3. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the 587 individuals who attempted suicide with a mean (+SD) age of 37.5 (+12.2) and years of education of 12.5 (+4.61).

Demographic and clinical characteristics		N	%
Gender	Female	510	86.9%
Marital Status	Single	229	39.1%
	Married	207	35.2%
	Divorced	102	17.4%
	Separated	40	6.8%
	Widow	9	1.5%
	Diagnosis	Major Depressive Disorder	395
Anxiety Disorders		430	73.2%
Bipolar Disorder		169	28.8%
Alcohol use disorder		165	28.1%
Eating disorder		156	26.6%
Substance use disorder		106	18.1%
Current Tobacco Smokers		336	57.2%

Table 4. Association of *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* combined activity scores with the severity of suicide (> percentile 75 of the “objective circumstance subscale” from the suicide intent scale; SIS) in patients that have attempted suicide

N= 587	<i>2D6+2C19</i> <4 “Low”	<i>2D6+2C19</i> =4; “Medium”	<i>2D6+2C19</i> >4 “High”
SIS-Objective circumstance subscale	n (%) 222 (37.8%)	n (%) 230 (39.2%)	n (%) 135 (23.0%)
> percentile 75 (n= 187)	59 (31.5%)	74 (39.6%)	54 (28.9%)
< percentile 75 (n= 400)	163 (40.7%)	156 (39.0%)	81 (20.3%)

Table 5. Association of *CYP2D6* with the severity of suicide (> percentile 75 of the “objective circumstance subscale” from the suicide intent scale; SIS) in patients that have attempted suicide

N= 587	<i>CYP2D6</i> =0	<i>CYP2D6</i> =0.5	<i>CYP2D6</i> =1	<i>CYP2D6</i> =1.5	<i>CYP2D6</i> =2	<i>CYP2D6</i> >2
SIS-Objective circumstance subscale	n (%) 22 (3.7%)	n (%) 4 (0.7%)	n (%) 205 (34.9%)	n (%) 20 (3.4%)	n (%) 305 (52.0%)	n (%) 31 (5.3%)
> percentile 75 (n=187)	7 (3.7%)	1 (0.5%)	59 (31.6%)	4 (2.1%)	103 (55.1%)	13 (7.0%)
< percentile 75 (n=400)	15 (3.8%)	3 (0.8%)	146 (36.5%)	16 (4.0%)	202 (50.5%)	18 (4.5%)

Table 6. Association of *CYP2C19* with the severity of suicide (> percentile 75 of the “objective circumstance subscale” from the suicide intent scale; SIS) in that have attempted suicide

N= 587	<i>CYP2C19</i> =0	<i>CYP2C19</i> =1	<i>CYP2C19</i> =2	<i>CYP2C19</i> =3	<i>CYP2C19</i> =4
SIS-Objective circumstance subscale	n (%) 9 (1.5%)	n (%) 98 (16.7%)	n (%) 282 (48.0%)	n (%) 182 (31.0%)	n (%) 16 (2.7%)
> percentile 75 (n=187)	2 (1.1%)	27 (14.4%)	87 (46.5%)	70 (37.4%)	1 (0.5%)
< percentile 75 (n=400)	7 (1.8%)	71 (17.8%)	195 (48.8%)	112 (28.0%)	15 (3.8%)

Figure 1. Definition of the three groups according to the combined drug metabolic capacity scores based on values assigned to *CYP2D6* and *CYP2C19* alleles in Table 1. A score below 4 corresponds to a low metabolic capacity; a score equal to 4 corresponds to a medium metabolic capacity and a score above 4, corresponds to a high metabolic capacity.

	CYP2D6=0	CYP2D6=0.5	CYP2D6=1	CYP2D6=1.5	CYP2D6=2	CYP2D6>2
CYP2C19=0	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
CYP2C19=1	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Medium
CYP2C19=2	Low	Low	Low	Low	Medium	High
CYP2C19=3	Low	Low	Medium	High	High	High
CYP2C19=4	Medium	High	High	High	High	High

Figure 2. Influence of the "combined CYP2D6-CYP2C19 metabolic capacity" (divided into three groups: low, medium and high) on the dimension of the SIS-Objective circumstances section (initial exploratory analysis).

